

European maize cropping systems: towards agroecology under climate change and breeding challenges

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Abstract

In 2021, about 15Mha of maize have been harvested in the European Union (EU-27), of which 9Mha were grain maize and 6Mha were silage maize, making maize the second most important crop after wheat in the EU-27. After decades of rapid yield gains ($130\text{-}150\text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{ yr}^{-1}$), grain maize yields have started to plateau both in France and Germany since 2001 and 2009, respectively. Average actual yields (8.9 t ha^{-1} in France, and 9.6 t ha^{-1} in Germany) are estimated to be 70-90% of the yield potential, indicating little opportunity for further yield increase, unless new varieties with higher yield potential become available. Currently, maize is mainly cultivated in cropping systems making an intensive use of nitrogen fertilizers ($194\text{ kgN ha}^{-1}\text{ yr}^{-1}$ on average in France) and irrigation water (32% of grain maize area is irrigated in France), rising concerns for associated environmental impacts. On the other hand, maize systems generally display relatively low pesticides use intensities (maize average TFI of 2.8 in France) despite being mainly grown in simplified rotations dominated by a few crops. Therefore, high productivity and low pesticides use intensity are two key advantages of maize production, but accumulating evidence show they are challenged by climate change. First, as climate is changing faster than expected, climate impacts emerge earlier (as soon as the 2030s) in new generation of climate and crop models, with impacts being more negative than previously estimated (yield may decrease by up to -10% to -20% in many parts of the EU without adaptation). Most important drivers of these projected yield losses are increased drought, heat, and their compound extremes, which poses specific challenges to breeding programs. Second, climate change is expected to modify the development of maize pests and diseases, leading to increasing risks of damages in many parts of Europe. This includes northward expansion of northern corn leaf blight, shifts in the relative importance of *Fusarium* species, more favorable conditions for *Aspergillus flavus* (and associated mycotoxins risks) as well as for insects' development. Breeding for durable multiple-disease multiple-insect resistance maize cultivars appears therefore as essential to keep pesticide use intensity of maize systems as low as possible. Looking forward, intercropping maize with other crop species may also be a very interesting option to cope with the above-mentioned challenges. Indeed, recent research provided evidence for benefits of intercropping with maize in both low-inputs and high-inputs cropping systems, with substantial yield gains, fertilizers savings, and better control of pests and diseases. Breeding maize cultivars adapted to intercropping is thus a promising although challenging avenue for breeders. Maize breeding is facing huge challenges due to climate change and the agroecological transition, and they are made even more complicated as climate is changing faster than expected, thus reducing time for adaptation.

Maize cultivation in Europe: towards agroecology under climate change and breeding challenges

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Take-home messages

- 1. Dominant maize systems in western Europe are high-inputs systems (except for pesticides) in which the exploitable yield gap has been (almost) closed**
- 2. Climate change is bringing a number of challenges to maize cultivation:**
 - Climate is changing faster than expected, thus reducing time for adaptation
 - Negative yield impacts of increasing drought and heat, and their compound extremes
 - Changes in pests and diseases
 - Need to explore « catastrophic » climate change scenarios
- 3. Intercropping as a path toward agroecology for maize**
 - Intercropping maize with other crops has benefits in both low- and high-inputs systems
 - This has implications for breeding

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Dominant maize systems in western Europe are high-inputs systems (except for pesticides) in which the exploitable yield gap has been (almost) closed

Maize harvested area in the EU

Harvested area of main crops in the EU-27 in 2021
(permanent pastures are excluded)

With 17% of croplands (of which 9 Mha are grain maize and 6Mha are silage maize),
maize is the second crop in the EU-27 after wheat

Grain maize yield trends in France and Germany

Maize yield gaps are low in France and Germany

Actual yield as % of yield potential

	France	Germany
Rainfed maize	88 %	88 %
Irrigated maize	72 %	-

→ There is little opportunity for further yield increase, unless new varieties with higher yield potential become available

Source: Global Yield Gap Atlas (www.yieldgap.org)

Schils et al. (2018). Cereal yield gaps across Europe. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 101, 109-120

Van Ittersum et al. (2013). Yield gap analysis with local to global relevance—a review. *Field Crops Research*, 143, 4-17.

Observed maize inputs levels in France (2017)

Importance of short rotations and no till for maize

Spatial distribution of simplified maize – cereals rotations in the EU over 2012-2018

About 50% of maize area in the EU is cultivated under simplified rotations in which average maize temporal frequency is ~80% and cereals ~20%.

% area under no-till in France

02

Climate change
is bringing a
number of
challenges to
maize
cultivation

Climate is changing faster than expected, thus reducing time for adaptation

Future warming over France

in black: whole year
in red: june-august

SSP2-4.5

SSP5-8.5

Climate impacts emerge earlier in new generation of climate and crop models

Simulated productivity (yield) time series for maize shown as relative changes to the 1983–2013 reference period under SSP126 (green) and SSP585 (yellow) at the global scale. Simulations: 5 Global Climate Models × 12 Global Gridded Crop Models.

And are more negative than previously estimated

Map showing median maize yield changes (2069–2099) under SSP585 across climate and crop models for current growing regions (>10 ha). Hatching indicates areas where <70% of the climate–crop model combinations agree on the sign of impact

- Results suggest **markedly more pessimistic yield responses** for maize, compared to the original ensemble.
- Mean end-of-century maize productivity is shifted **from +5% to -6% (SSP126)** and **from +1% to -24% (SSP585)**—explained by warmer climate projections and improved crop model sensitivities

Climate change has negative impacts on maize yields due to increasing drought and heat, and their compound extremes

The frequency of compound drought and heat and is increasing, globally and in Europe

Trends in the spatial extent of global maize area exposed to concurrent hot and dry extremes.

The Guardian

Climate crisis made summer drought 20 times more likely, scientists find

Record northern hemisphere drought in 2022 hit crops and power stations, worsening food and energy crises

Damian Carrington
Environment editor

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Wed 5 Oct 2022 22:00 BST

Climate change will likely change maize pests and diseases and associated yield risks

Potential impacts of climate change on maize cultivation, mycotoxigenic fungi, and plant-pathogen interactions

1. Shifts in existing diseases complexes
2. New pathogens that are moving northward with warming

Risk maps for aflatoxin contamination in maize at harvest in 3 different climate scenarios

Expected increased risk from insect pests from global warming

Mediterranean corn borer
Sesamia nonagrioides

Western corn root worm
Diabrotica virgifera virgifera

European corn borer
Ostrinia nubilalis

Fall armyworm
Spodoptera frugiperda

- many insect pests (including ECB) will migrate northward and new invasive species (e.g. Mediterranean corn borer, fall armyworm) are likely to invade NW Europe
- More generations per year, expansion of frost-free areas due to warming
- more direct (e.g., feeding, sucking) and indirect (e.g., creating wounds facilitating pathogen entry, pathogen transmission) damages are expected in Europe

Challenges for breeding

- Drought and heat tolerance deserve high priority in future crop breeding programs
- As well as breeding for durable multiple-disease and multiple-insect resistance
- Breeding simultaneously for many goals might involve trade-offs (for example between water use efficiency and thermoregulation when breeding for heat and drought)
- Climate is changing faster than expected, with negative impacts likely to emerge earlier than anticipated, thus reducing time for adaptation
- Anticipating the diversity of future climate conditions (and uncertainty): a key for breeders?
- Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios?

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Intercropping as a path toward agroecology for maize

Intercropping

Relay-strip intercrop of maize and wheat in the Netherlands

(Source: J. Evers, Wageningen University and Research)

According to previous meta-analysis
Land Efficiency Ratio (LER) = 1.2 to 1.3

(i.e, intercropping can produce ~20–30% more total food from a piece of cropland than when each crop is grown in monoculture on said piece of land)

BUT absolute yield gains might be low under low inputs (low yielding) systems

Intercropping has also benefits under high inputs cropping systems

- Global meta-analysis of > 900 intercropping experiments
- Results revealed **two syndromes of production**: the high-input and the low-input intercropping strategies
- The high-input intercropping strategy provided **yield gains that were about four times larger** than the low-input strategy
- Both the low- and high-yield intercropping strategies **saved 16–29% of the land and 19–36% of the fertilizer** compared with monocultures

A modern intensive version of intercropping

Photo from Raza et al. (2022). *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13.

The high-input syndrome has 3 distinguishing features:

1. Crops are are planted in alternating strips
2. Intensive use of fertilizers and pesticides
3. Maize is often one of the two crops used

Temporal niche differentiation. Yield benefit of intercropping tended to be larger when one crop grows best early in the growing season (such as wheat, barley and faba bean), and the other grows best in the heat of mid-to-late summer, such as maize.

Intercropping to control pests and diseases

Summary of the vote counting analysis on **pests in intercropping**

Result of vote counting analysis on the effect of intercropping on **disease incidence or severity** in published literature on annual intercrop

Challenges for breeding

- **“Living and performing with others, breeding plant teams”** : breeding for traits that maximized yields when intercropped rather than when grown in monoculture (traits to increase complementarity or facilitation, for production of volatiles that deter pests etc.)
- **Breeding for low-inputs and high-inputs systems**
- Complex interactions that drive resource capture and distribution in intercropped systems could be better understood through **resource-based modelling** to explore how specific traits can be optimized for complementarity

Conclusion and perspectives

- Maize is mainly cultivated in high-inputs cropping systems in the EU (except for pesticides), actual yield being close to the yield potential
- Climate change is likely to challenge maize performances, with increasing drought and heat and their compound extremes, as well as important changes in pests and diseases. Breeding efforts are key to contribute addressing these challenges.
- Climate is changing faster than expected: a big challenge is to pursue many different breeding targets in a short time
- Intercropping appears as a promising path toward agroecology for maize systems with benefits in terms of yield, nitrogen use efficiency and control of pests and diseases. Breeding for intercropped maize deserve high attention
- Exploring catastrophic climate change scenarios?